

LEADERSHIP STYLE PREFERENCES OF BSU-BUGUIAS CAMPUS FACULTY AND STAFF

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ABSTRACT

This causal-comparative study reviewed the leadership style preferences of faculty and staff of Benguet State University- Buguias Campus. A Total of 72 participants completed the research questionnaire consisting of demographic questions and the Vannsimpco Leadership Survey. A single factor, one way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) was conducted and significant differences were identified within the nine leadership styles preferences namely, ($F [8, 639] = 47.25, p < 0.01$). The statistical analysis showed collective preferences toward Democratic-Transformational Leadership ($M=4.88$), Democratic Leadership ($M=4.48$), Transformational Leadership ($M=4.46$). The Least preferred style was Laissez-faire Leadership ($M=2.85$). This study also compared leadership style preferences of participants classified as faculty versus those classified as staff. Significant differences were identified within responses for Democratic Leadership and Transactional Leadership styles.

Keywords: *leadership style, preferences, Laissez-faire, Democratic, Transactional*

INTRODUCTION

In any educational institution, leadership role is regarded as indispensable. The job of any leader is primarily meant to guide and lead the individuals in the right direction. In this way, they will be able to carry out their duties satisfactorily as well as overcome problems and challenges that may arise within the course of implementation of their roles. The heads, directors and principals of schools are the ones vested with the authority to play

leadership roles. The educators are also required to be effective leaders in guiding students towards the right direction and helping them to achieve academic goals.

It is a continuous debate whether leadership comes from the personal qualities of a leader or a leader makes followership through what she /he does or believes (Grint 2004). Grint also highlight position problems, he posed whether leadership is the true authority to decide or implement, or it is only a person in front who takes his/her directions for someone. Recent reviews take leadership as “a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal (Northouse 2004). Another view about leadership is that it is like the Abominable Snowman, whose footprints are everywhere but who is nowhere to be seen” (Bennis and Nanus 1985). In short leadership/leader is either a person who is in charge and has authorities to take decision and also has powers to implement his/her decisions or a process having a set of other authoritative process about organization, personal or social process of influence for which the groups, teams or organizations can do more to increase their ability. The selection of the leader not only depends on the personal characteristics of the person, but also on the social and cultural factors along with his/her exposure towards life (Bolden 2010). It is then important to include the demographic profiles of respondents in this research endeavor as leadership capabilities of a leader does not only depend on personal characteristics but is also affected by social and cultural factors.

Leadership in education is a multidimensional research area. There is no denying that the most researched field in the behavioral sciences is leadership. Still, leadership theory concepts have eluded managers like a haunting melody. Much has been read, but there is not a much clearer picture in the available literature. Thus, it is essential for the individuals to hone their leadership skills. It is the main duty of the leaders to ensure and make provision for appropriate information for them to lead colleagues and to achieve the educational goals and objectives and bring about success in the overall system of education. Leaders need to provide their constituents with sufficient support and assistance to perform their tasks and activities. Leithwood et. al (2006) also mentioned that leadership is a high priority issue for many people concerned with education these days. Reformers depend on it. The public believes that it is what schools need more of thus, it is not surprising then that so many people are trying to make a living peddling their latest insights about effective educational leadership. Indeed leadership by adjective is a growth industry. We have instructional leadership, transformational leadership, moral leadership, constructivist leadership, servant leadership, cultural leadership, and primal leadership (Goleman, Boyatzis & McKee, 2002).

Leadership was integrated into the academic vocabulary of organizational studies as a term from our everyday language without being redefined. "It's not shocking, therefore, that the meanings of the term are almost as numerous as the scholars involved in their research." For example, Bennis (1989) said that "leadership is like beauty, it's difficult to define, but when you see it, you know it." Chemers (1997) offers the following

standard definition: "Leadership is a system of social influence in which one person may enlist others help and support in the fulfillment of a common task." The only assumption shared by this and most definitions is that "leadership involves a process of social influence in which one individual deliberately exerts influence over other in order to structure group or organization activities and relationships. Exploring therefore of leadership preferences of subordinates may help leaders on the guide in dealing with co-employees.

The leader in an organization can have such an impact on their followers' performance and whether or not they will stay in the organization, it is then important to study followers' preference for their leader's behaviors (Howell & Costley, 2001; Buckingham & Coffman, 1999) thus, this research is conducted.

Rain (2020) stated that the advantage to understanding your leadership style is that you understand your strengths and weaknesses. You can be proactive and more effective as a leader by strategically using your strengths and counteracting your weaker areas. Your style defines your values and perspective, and being aware of it will aid your communication to those you work with. As the saying goes, knowledge is power. You can empower yourself and move forward in your career or interest by exercising this knowledge thus, this research is conducted to explore the leadership preferences of BSU-BC employees and to determine possible leadership styles that is of importance at present.

Further, this study should provide insights into best practices for schools and companies to use with different generations that might affect leadership effectiveness. Information from this study can be used by the human resource unit in developing leadership training and development interventions to enhance the effectiveness of leaders in their organization. Moreover, the result of this study will be used in enhancing the institutions' policies on assigning since individuals in Human Resource Development (HRD) are concerned about improving human performance and unleashing human potential (Gilley, et al., 2002; Swanson & Holton, 2001), learning more about characteristics of people who work in organizations benefits the field of HRD. Increasing HRD's ability to address generational issues in regards to leadership in the workplace is critical to improving an organization's performance.

Improper leadership style is a problem for each public educational organization. The most important abnormal response is the dissatisfaction that appear among staff at educational organizations which considerably reduces the amount of their performance. Managers' role is to recognize the right style of leadership based on various condition and relation for applying it in an educational organization. Many managers do not have adequate awareness and skill for generating suitable atmosphere among staff and to apply precise style at workplace. Hence, all educational organizations need to have correctly educated and aware managers for improving and managing affairs of the

organization. This study will explore the leadership style preferences of BSU-Buguias Campus faculty and staff for possible leadership trainings and seminars.

Basit et.al (2017) in their research titled “Impact of leadership style on employee performance (a case study on a private organization in Malaysia) found that there is a significant and positive impact of democratic and laissez-faire leadership styles on employee performance while autocratic leadership is found to have a negative significant impact on employee performance. Through foregoing importance of leadership styles and its impact to employees’ performance, it is therefore the aim of this research to explore the leadership preferences and to determine possible significant differences of leadership preferences between faculty and staff of Benguet State university-Buguias Campus.

Transformational Leadership Style is the darling of the leadership studies discipline, the transformational leadership method was first elaborated upon through the historical research of Burns (1978) and, later, Bass (1985). According to these works, effective transformational leadership transcends the limitations imposed by followers and organizational structure.

Burns (2003) explains, transformational leaders “cause a metamorphosis in the form or structure, a change in the very condition or nature of thing, a change into another substance, a radical change in outward form or inner character” (p. 24). These leaders achieve their results through personal charisma, charm, clear vision, and passion.

Followers of transformational leaders believe themselves valued as an individual, and often feel empowered to perform better. Transformational leadership assumes institutions need, and require, a transformation; that innovation is always preferable to the status quo, and that followers are eager to be have personal and intimate relationships with their leaders. In many ways, this definition explains as much about the researchers’ world view as it does the leadership he or she is purporting to study. If one believes in the need for constant innovation for the sake of innovation, it makes sense why transformation leadership is appealing. Many followers or organizations may not want transformation or to form emotional connections to their leader, perceiving this attempts to establish emotional bonds as poor management or emotional manipulation.

Furthermore, followers may misconstrue the emotional appeals of transformational leaders and become overly dependent upon their leader for personal validation (Stone, Russell, & Patterson, 2003). Transformational leadership can be used by leaders who lack moral guidance and seek to wield the “dark side of charisma” (Yukl, 1989) for less than desirable reasons. Although some advocates maintain that “authentic transformational leadership foster the moral values of honesty, loyalty, and fairness,” nevertheless, one cannot ignore how the traits of the transformational leader have been used for nefarious purposes. It is this realization, demonstrated through historical experiences that should place some caution upon the degree to which transformational leadership is celebrated by educators.

Since the turn of the twenty-first century, it has become more evident that effective leaders must pay close attention to the leadership style expectations of their followers, as this correlates to key factors such as employee satisfaction, retention and adherence to organizational goals (Notgrass, 2014). Complex entities such as HEIs work under mandatory policies with frequent change, creating a need for perceptive leaders at all levels to preserve stability and sustainable growth. Continued research on the perspective of followers within colleges and universities is necessary for enhanced awareness, as it not only impacts leader-follower relationships, but also student success, public perception, and financial well-being (Alonderiene & Majauskaite, 2016; Harris, Hinds, Manansingh, Rubino, & Morote, 2016). It is then important to explore the leadership preferences of BSU-Buguias campus faculty and staff to see whether there is a significant difference between their responses as Leithwood et.al (2006) stated that leadership is a high priority issue for many people concerned with education these days.

Leadership in education is a multidimensional research area. There is no denying that the most researched field in the behavioral sciences is leadership. Still, leadership theory concepts have eluded managers like a haunting melody. Much has been read, but there is not a much clearer picture in the available literature. Mews (2019) found through statistical analysis showed collective preferences toward Democratic-Transformational, democratic leadership, transformational leadership, and transactional leadership. The research result also showed that the least preferred leadership style was laissez-fair. Furthermore, significant differences were identified with in responses for democratic leadership and transactional leadership styles. This research result will further be validated in this research. Moreover, Kamisa and Wafa (2014) research result showed that the three major ethnic groups in Sabah appear to have similar leadership preference. In addition, no significant difference was found between leadership preferences and the demographic variables.

The research of Church (2012) verified in an ecclesiastical setting what is already known in the government, education, manufacturing, and other industry settings: Transformational leadership style, as perceived by the leader, is correlated with organizational growth the research determined that there is certainly a correlation between district superintendents' perceptions of their leadership styles and organizational growth as measured by church membership and worship attendance in the North American districts of the Church of the Nazarene (COTN). This research result is important in this study for it will explore the possibility of significant differences between the leadership preferences of faculty and staff of the campus.

Moreover, Kalu et al (2018) concluded that the major challenges leaders face in improving job performance of subordinates are that of subordinates not reporting to the leader who delegated authority, high expectations by subordinates from the leader and attitude of subordinates towards the leader. It is further recommended among others that subordinates who are delegated to do something should be made to know from the

beginning that they should report back to the leader. It is suggested that subsequent researches will investigate other area such as Perception of subordinates on the leadership styles adopted by management of various libraries. Thus, this research will be conducted.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Survey method was utilized in this study since leadership styles preferences of faculty and staff will be explored.

Research Locale and Participants

The respondents of this study are thirty-three (37) faculty and thirty-two (35) non-teaching staff of Benguet State University-Buguias Campus, Loo, Buguias, Benguet.

Research Instrument

This paper adapted the survey questionnaire developed by Drs. Barry Vann, Aaron Coleman, and Jennifer in the year 2014 because of its validity and versatility. The VLS provides reliable feedback on nine leadership styles: transactional; democratic; autocratic; autocratic-transformational; autocratic-transactional; democratic-transformational; democratic-transactional; transformational, and laissez fair. The instrument has two parts. Part I includes the profile of respondents: highest educational attainment, job status (Non –Teaching/Teaching), and length of experience. Part II consisted of 27 items whom the respondents will rate based from five scales : 5- Strongly Agree (SA); 4- Agree (A); 3-Neutral (N); 2- Disagree (D), 1- Strongly Disagree (SD). The questionnaire was again subjected for validity by the researchers. The reliability result using Cronbach's Alpha was 0.92 which indicates good reliability or internal consistency of the instrument.

Data Collection Procedure

The survey questionnaires were distributed and retrieved personally by the researchers after following the research protocols of the campus.

Data Analysis

To address the problems posed in the study, gathered data will be analyzed accordingly, frequency counts and rankings will be used to determine the leadership style preferences of respondents while Microsoft Excel and SPSS will be used to identify whether significant correlation exist between leadership style preference and demographic profile of respondents Inferential statistics were used to analyze if significant

correlation exist between the leadership style preference and profile of respondents. , and using mean coefficient to determine which leadership style preferences BSU-Buguias employees' preferred the most and the least preferred. A series of independent samples t-test were conducted to distinguish if there's a significant difference between leadership style preferences of teaching and non-teaching staff.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Higher education institutions are complex and continuously-evolving organizations that require effective leaders who understand and embrace the preferences of their followers. As detailed previously, key factors such as employee job satisfaction and commitment are impacted by the leadership approach utilized by the leader(s) of the organization (Alonderiene & Majauskaite, 2016; Lussier & Achua, 2012; Northouse, 2015). While a clear need for further examination into leadership style preferences from the follower's perspective was evident based on the literature review, this viewpoint had been misrepresented through existing research (Alonderiene & Majauskaite, 2016; Eacott, 2011). This study helped address the gap in research and add value for future examination of leadership preferences within organizations. This study was developed to assess the two specific areas. The first was a comprehensive review of leadership style preferences among faculty and staff in BSU-Buguias Campus as a collective group. The second was to determine whether leadership style preferences differed between participants classified as faculty and those classified as staff.

Table 1 shows the summary of the collective preferences of the employees of BSU-Buguias for Democratic-Transformational Leadership (M=4.68), Democratic Leadership (M=4.48), Transactional Leadership (M=4.46) and Transformational Leadership (M=4.43), while the least preferred style was Laissez- faire (M=2.85). Additional statistical assessment using the single factor, one-way ANOVA was conducted on the responses, to identify significant differences in leadership style preferences among the participants within the nine leadership styles as shown in Table 2.

Given that multiple leadership styles were preferred by the participants in this study, the findings suggest that a situational approach may be necessary to effectively lead in a college or university setting. This notion aligns with existing research on situational leadership, supporting the leader's need to dictate his or her style based on the environment and followers, especially in complex organizations such as HEIs (Khan, 2017). In order to utilize the situational approach effectively, the leader must get to know his or her followers, identify their needs and preferences, and adjust leadership styles as necessary (Northouse, 2015). This supports the notion that effective leaders should employ a full range of leadership behaviors based on the situation (Avolio & Bass, 2002).

Table 1. Summary of Leadership Style Preferences

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
TRANSACTIONAL	72	321.3333	4.462963	0.270909
DEMOCRATIC	72	322.3333	4.476852	0.321835
AUTOCRATIC	72	237	3.291667	1.793232
AUTOCRATIC TRANSFORMATIONAL	72	287.6667	3.99537	0.589963
AUTOCRATIC TRANSACTIONAL	72	250.6667	3.481482	0.547383
DEMOCRATIC TRANSFORMATIONAL	72	337	4.680556	0.25489
DEMOCRATIC TRANSACTIONAL	72	298.6667	4.148148	0.63815
TRANSFORMATIONAL	72	321.3333	4.431963	0.311598
LAISSEZ FAIRE	72	205	2.847222	0.822966

The Democratic-Transformational Leadership style can be used during times of change when involvement and inclusion are desired from followers regarding the decision-making and communication process. This style can also be adopted when mentoring opportunities are presented, both for the leader and for emerging employees (Vann et al., 2014). Since it is a hybrid leadership style, the leader may need to utilize more or less Democratic or Transformational Leadership strategies, depending on the situation.

Table 2. Single factor one-way ANOVA-leadership styles

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	233.142	8	29.14275	47.25062	9.52E-60	1.952877
Within Groups	394.1158	639	0.61677			
Total	627.2577	647				

Democratic Leadership is a collaborative style that can be effective with creative groups and select followers who are open to new ideas. This approach can also lead to the discovery of untapped potential in training or professional development settings (Bavelas & Lewin, 1942; Rustin & Armstrong, 2012). Based on the findings in this study, Democratic Leadership would be more appropriate with faculty than staff, since there is a significant difference in preference between the two groups of employees.

Leaders can practice Transformational Leadership when their followers begin to plateau or decline in performance (Lussier & Achua, 2012). Transformational Leadership is often utilized to motivate followers and achieve at a higher rate through inspirational motivation and individualized consideration (Northouse, 2015). This is a leadership style

preferred by both faculty and staff, and should be employed for relationship-building and continued progress in performance.

For followers who are relied on for repetitive or daily tasks, a Transactional Leadership approach may be best-suited (Lussier & Achua, 2012). This leadership style is incentive-based, and ideal for roles where projects and deadlines are the priority (Hamstra, et al., 2014). This study revealed a significant difference in preferences toward Transactional Leadership, indicating a higher preference from faculty than staff. Given the contrast between employee groups, leaders in HEIs can benefit from understanding key aspects of all leadership styles and be prepared to adjust based on the situation.

A series of independent samples t-tests were conducted whether leadership style preferences differed between those classified as faculty and those classified as staff. The data were assessed for each of the nine leadership styles and the results revealed significant difference in preferences toward Democratic Leadership and Transactional Leadership. Faculty participants scored Democratic Leadership (M=4.61) and Transactional Leadership (M=4.28) highest of the nine styles, while staff participants scored both styles lower. These results are worth noting, as HEI leaders with supervisory responsibilities for both faculty and staff may need to adjust their approach based on the roles of their subordinates.

Table 2. Summary of independent samples t-tests for a comparison of leadership style preferences between faculty and staff

Leadership Tested	Style	Teaching Mean	Non-teaching Mean	Results		Significant Difference
				<i>t-stat</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
DEMO-TRANSACTIONAL		4.21	4.09	0.6423	0.5228	No
DEMO-TRANSFORMATIONAL		4.54	4.56	1.9628	0.0541	No
AUTO-TRANSFORMATIONAL		4.12	3.87	1.3920	0.1683	No
TRANSFORMATIONAL		4.55	4.31	0.9791	0.3308	No
DEMOCRATIC		4.61	3.41	2.4173	0.0182	Yes
TRANSACTIONAL		4.79	3.37	2.9248	0.0047	Yes
AUTOCRATIC		2.86	3.74	1.3630	0.1480	No
LAISSEZ-FAIRE		2.98	2.70	1.3023	0.1971	No
AUTO-TRANSACTIONAL		3.61	3.34	1.5781	0.1195	No

Critical value $f_{0.05}(8, inf.)= 1.94$

Critical value $f_{0.01}(8, inf.)= 2.51$

Reference: Ronald E Walpole. INTRODUCTION TO STATISTICS Second Edition pg. 310

Conclusions

This study addressed a gap in research by assessing leadership style preferences among faculty and staff in higher education institutions. The findings showed an overall preference toward Democratic-Transformational Leadership ($M = 4.25$), with additional support for Democratic Leadership ($M = 4.21$), Transformational Leadership ($M = 4.21$), and Transactional Leadership ($M = 4.20$). The least preferred style was Laissez-faire Leadership ($M = 2.63$). A single factor, one-way ANOVA found significant differences within the nine leadership styles.

Significant differences in leadership style preferences were identified between participants classified as faculty and those classified as staff. Independent samples t-tests revealed significant differences in preference toward Democratic Leadership and Transactional Leadership. Faculty participants preferred Democratic Leadership ($M = 4.30$) and Transactional Leadership ($M = 4.28$) at a significantly higher level than staff participants (lower than $M = 3.42$ for both styles).

The conclusions provide a sense of which leadership styles are preferred, while also acknowledging that followers may prefer a different leadership approach than others based on their role. These findings can be used to provide awareness for current and future leaders within complex organizations such as HEIs. The results can also aid future studies involving organizational and higher education leadership as the underrepresented viewpoint of the follower continues to be examined.

Recommendations

Based on the study's conclusions, recommendations include the Empower the specified leadership style together with its auxiliary attributes. To support leadership effectiveness, triangulate results using leaders' sourced viewpoints data and qualitative methodologies. Subsequent investigations could broaden the scope of this analysis by incorporating more participants from additional HEIs. Extra demographic inquiries, such as those concerning work satisfaction and dedication from employees, may offer proof to substantiate the relationship between preferred leadership styles and employee job satisfaction.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers demonstrated exemplary conduct throughout the study, adhering to research standards by employing appropriate language, methodologies, and comments. Initial steps involved obtaining permission from relevant authorities within the university, whose endorsement paved the way for data collection. Clear communication about the study's purpose was provided to respondents both verbally and through a letter accompanying the survey guide. The respondents were assured of their autonomy to choose which interview questions to answer. To ensure confidentiality, responses were

treated with utmost privacy, and respondents were randomly approached for follow-up interviews. The researchers sought explicit permission for the utilization of respondents' responses for the study's intended purpose. In the subsequent analysis, interpretation, and discussion, the researchers maintained objectivity and impartiality, transitioning seamlessly from respondents' individual experiences to the broader universal essence of the subject under consideration. This work received no specific grant from any funding agency. The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest

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